

Changes in Climate Change Rating of Countries 2020-2021

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Abstract

This work is related to the Climate Change Rating of Countries (CCR). The parameters included in the rating are CO₂ emissions per capita and per GDP, cumulative CO₂ emissions in the last 30 years, and change of emissions in the last 10 years. The parameters are compared to the world averages. A lower CCR value results in a better rating. The A-G rating of countries is according to groups within the rating limits. The best rating (A) is for the lowest CCR.

In 2021 was a major change in Group G, the worst CCR group. The CO₂ emissions of the countries in Group G increased by 35%, as the USA moved to this group in 2021 from Group F.

The only OECD country in the best CCR group, Group A, moved to Group B.

In 2021 the world CCR changed from 100 to 101.4 moving from Group E to Group F, the Red Group. The main reason for this change was the world's CO₂ per capita, which increased in 2021 by 4.3%.

Keywords:

Climate Change, Global Warming, CO₂ emissions, CO₂ per capita, CO₂ per GDP, CO₂ emissions per capita, CO₂ emissions per GDP, Climate Change Rating, Global Warming of countries, climate justice, carbon justice

Glossary

Ave	average
CCO2	global cumulative CO2 emissions according to publication [1] [4], CO2 emissions produced from fossil fuels and cement production only – land use change is not included, tCO2
CCp\$\$	country's cumulative CO2 emissions in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period
CCR	Climate Change Rating of countries according to this work
CGP	Conservative Global Parameter, decreasing only world parameter applied to the CCR
CO2	emissions of Carbon Dioxide, CO ₂
Cp\$	country's CO2 emissions per GDP in the last year, tCO2/\$GDP (ton CO2 per year, per \$GDP 2017 per year)
Cp\$10	country's change in Cp\$ in last 10 years, tCO2/\$GDP
CpC	country's CO2 emissions per capita in the last year, tCO2/y,cap
CpC10	country's change in CpC in last 10 years, tCO2/y,cap
GDP	Gross Domestic Product, constant international \$ 2017, \$GDP/y
Global Warming	global surface temperature change over land+ocean above 1850-1900 baseline, °C
MtCO2/y	Mega-ton CO2 = 1,000,000 metric tons of CO2
OWID	Our World in Data – Internet site [1] [4]
Ref	reference
tCO2	metric ton of CO2
tCO2/y,cap	metric ton of CO ₂ per year, per capita
WB	World Bank

Climate Change Rating of Countries

The Climate Change Rating of Countries system (CCR) is described in the publication [1].

The CCR values for 2020 were calculated in publications [1] [2] [3] and for 2021 in [4] [5].

Parameters Included in the Rating

Parameters included in the CCR rating

- CO2 emissions per capita, CpC
- CO2 emissions per GDP, Cp\$
- Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period, CCp\$\$
- Change in CpC in the last 10 years, CPC10
- Change in Cp\$ in the last 10 years, CP\$10

A higher CCR means more CO2 emissions.

Changes in Climate Change Rating 2020-2021

Table 1 - Number of countries in A-G groups

Group	2020	2021	Change	Change
A	13	7	-6	-46.2%
B	24	31	+7	+29.2%
C	30	22	-8	-26.7%
D	44	51	+7	+15.9%
E	35	33	-2	-5.7%
F	34	35	+1	+2.9%
G	28	29	+1	+3.6%

Table 2 - Number of countries in A-D and E-G groups

Groups	2020	2021	Change
A-D	111	111	+0.0%
E-G	97	97	+0.0%

Groups A-D may be regarded as “green” groups of countries with lower CO₂ intensity and better CCR rating, and groups E-G may be regarded as “black” groups with higher CO₂ intensity and worse CCR rating.

Table 3 - CO₂ emissions of countries in A-G groups, tCO₂/y

Group	2020	2021	Change	Change
A	64,240,675	34,633,646	-29,607,029	-46.1%
B	452,596,360	469,833,167	+17,236,807	+3.8%
C	1,289,499,182	309,543,829	-979,955,353	-76.0%
D	2,947,234,126	4,132,825,141	+1,185,591,015	+40.2%
E	4,553,560,059	4,274,034,234	-279,525,825	-6.1%
F	8,567,596,157	4,691,393,418	-3,876,202,739	-45.2%
G	16,440,549,561	22,179,477,991	+5,738,928,430	+34.9%

In 2021 Group G (the black group, above 50% of the CCR world average) CO₂ emissions increased by 35%.

Table 4 - CO₂ emissions of countries in A-D and E-G groups, tCO₂/y

Groups	2020	%	2021	%	Change	Change
A-D	4,753,570,343	14%	4,946,835,783	14%	+193,265,440	+4.1%
E-G	29,561,705,777	86%	31,144,905,643	86%	+1,583,199,866	+5.4%
Σ	34,315,276,120		36,091,741,426		+1,776,465,306	+5.2%

Table 5 - CCR of Group G, tCO₂/y

Groups	2020	%	2021	%	Change	Change
A-F	17,874,726,559	52%	13,912,263,435	39%	-3,962,463,124	-22.2%
G	16,440,549,561	48%	22,179,477,991	61%	+5,738,928,430	+34.9%

In 2020 the CO₂ emissions of Group G were below the sum of all other groups (A-F), while in 2021 the CO₂ emissions of Group G increased from 39% to 61% of the world's CO₂ emissions in 2021.

Group G added in 2021 5,739 MtCO₂, compared to all other groups decrease of 3,962 MtCO₂.

Table 6 - Groups average CCR

Group	2020	2021	Δ
A	43.1	38.0	-5.0
B	55.5	54.9	-0.6
C	65.8	65.5	-0.3
D	77.2	77.9	+0.8
E	91.9	92.7	+0.8
F	120.9	117.4	-3.6
G	209.6	211.6	+1.9

Countries Below and Above the World CCR

Table 7 - Countries below the world CCR and their CO2 emissions

	2020	2021	Change
number countries	146	145	-0.7%
%	70.2%	69.7%	
tCO2/y	9,307,130,402	9,895,624,017	+6.3%
%	27.1%	27.4%	

Table 8 - Countries above the world CCR and their CO2 emissions

	2020	2021	Change
number countries	62	63	+1.6%
%	29.8%	30.3%	
tCO2/y	25,008,145,718	26,196,117,409	4.8%
%	72.9%	72.6%	

Change in the World Rating

Table 9 - World CCR in 2021

Parameter	2021	CGP 2021	2021/CGP	Weight	CCR 2021
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	0.000328	0.000328	100%	20%	20.0%
CO2 emissions per capita	4.56	4.38	104%	25%	26.1%
CO2 emissions per GDP	0.000268	0.000268	100%	25%	25.0%
Last CpC to CpC before 10 years	97%	95%	102%	15%	15.3%
Last Cp\$ to Cp\$ before 10 years	81%	81%	100%	15%	15.0%
Σ				100%	101.4%

The world CCR was 100 in 2020, Group E, Violet group.

The world's CO₂ intensity increased in 2021 resulting in a CCR rating of 101.4, which is Group F, the Red group.

The main reason for this change is a 4.3% increase in CO₂ emissions per capita in 2021.

Climate Change Rating of Countries on the Website

The Climate Change Rating of countries according to this work is available on the website nowagreen.com/ccr [6].

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